

Finalized Coding Frame

Social environmental conditions¹			
Category	Code	Sub-themes	Description
Industry	Industry-embedded expectations for innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expectation to create something new to stay relevant in the industry • Expectation to remain creative to work in the industry • Expectation to stay updated on industry norms and trends 	Captures the social expectation and pressure in the industry to continuously create something new, remain creative, and stay updated on emerging norms and trends to remain relevant.
Industry	High industry-wide skill expectations and competition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously rising skill expectations in the industry • Pressure to upskill and improve compared to others in the industry • Pressure to stand out in the industry • Constant competition as a shared industry norm 	Captures the social climate of working in an industry where rising skill expectations and constant competition fuel continuous social pressure to upskill and compare oneself with peers.
Industry	Industry visibility and public exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expectations and pressure caused by the visibility and exposure of one's work outputs in the industry • Expectations and pressure based on one's reputation in the industry • Fear of public judgment due to visibility and public exposure of one's work 	Captures the social climate of working in an industry where the outcomes of one's work are inherently visible and subject to public evaluation, creating unease and fear of not meeting the perceived social expectations of industry actors.
Organizational	Ambiguous organizational norms and expectations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear expectations regarding one's work • Unclear norms for how work should be conducted 	Captures an organizational social climate where uncertainty stemming from vague or inconsistent social norms and expectations leaves employees either overestimating these expectations or unsure of how to meet them.
Organizational	Reserved organizational climate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational climate discouraging open discussion • Closed and reserved organizational social atmosphere 	Captures a workplace social climate where open discussion and expression feel discouraged, creating a closed and restrained social environment that can limit communication,

			support, and the formation of shared social norms and expectations.
Organizational	Organizational pressure to handle multiple roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expectation and pressure to manage various roles • Expectation and pressure to manage multiple tasks • Expectation and pressure to manage diverse responsibilities 	Captures the perceived social expectations and pressure from organizational actors that push employees to juggle multiple roles, tasks, and responsibilities, often making employees feel that they have little room to refuse or set boundaries.
Team/pair	Team/pair diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differences in professional background • Differences in educational background • Differences in areas of expertise • Differences in levels of expertise 	Captures team or pair social climates where differences in professional and educational backgrounds, levels of expertise, and skill sets can complicate collaboration and the formation of shared social norms and expectations.
Team/pair	Team/pair interdependence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressure for one's work output to be compatible with others • Pressure for one's work output to be timely with others • Pressure created by dependence on others' work outputs 	Captures social expectations arising from the interdependence of workflows (one's work output must be compatible with other's workflows), and the social pressure caused by being reliant on others within teams or pairs.
Team/pair	Team/pair expectation–reality mismatch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unrealistic expectations toward one's work • Insufficient understanding of one's work realities 	Captures social tensions that emerge when team or pair members misunderstand each other's actual work realities or constraints, causing unrealistic social expectations.
Team/pair	(Conflicting) team/pair IT use habits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expectations or pressure caused by preferring differing/conflicting IT • Expectations or pressure caused by preferring differing/conflicting IT versions • Expectations or pressure caused by preferring differing/conflicting IT use habits 	Captures social pressure and expectations arising from conflicting IT use preferences and habits within teams or pairs, creating pressure to either adapt or conform.

¹ Only the social environmental conditions that were identified to contribute to employees' IT use demands were included in the finalized coding frame.